

Development and validation of a framework to predict the linear stability of transverse thermoacoustic modes of a reheat combustor

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ABSTRACT

To achieve fully carbon-neutral, fuel-flexible and on-demand grid power delivery, gas turbines featuring constant pressure sequential combustion architecture show great potential. A sequential combustor is comprised of two axially-staged combustion chambers with the first stage typically being a swirl-stabilised propagating flame. Post first stage combustion, the exhaust stream is first diluted with air and later enriched with additional fuel in the second stage resulting in a vitiated product mixture at high temperatures leading to auto-ignition. Thermoacoustically-stable combustion stages are critical to ensure low emissions, high reliability and ensure mechanical integrity. The second stage firing under auto-ignition conditions can be subject to transversal instabilities. This article presents a finite element coupled method to model the thermoacoustic behaviour of a second stage reheat flame in an efficient, cost-effective approach. To do so, prior techniques to model the response of autoignition-stabilised flames to longitudinal acoustic perturbations is leveraged to quantify the auto-ignition flame's heat release rate response to transverse acoustic waves. Subsequently, the framework is used to compute the stability of transverse eigenmodes for an atmospheric reheat combustor. Validation is performed by comparison to experimentally obtained pressure sensor measurements and chemiluminescence imaging of the flame. It is observed that the framework can correctly predict the combustor's unstable first transverse mode and also capture the dynamic flame response qualitatively. Consequently, the framework presented in this work can be leveraged to get reliable and time-efficient stability estimates of the transverse thermoacoustic modes in experimental reheat burners.

1. Introduction

With the current strive to lower global carbon emissions and obtain climate neutral energy solutions as defined in the Paris agreement in 2015 [1], future power systems will need to be based on renewable energy sources (RES) [2–4]. Due to the strongly fluctuating nature of common RES such as wind and solar energy, gas turbines (GT) firing alternative carbon free fuels is predicted to be an ideal climate neutral asset to supply centralised large scale on-demand power to the grid [3,5–8]. Thereby, during the transition phase to completely carbon free GT power production, high fuel flexibility [9] and quick ramp up times are key. To enable variable fuel combustion and various mixing ratios thereof e.g. hydrogen/ammonia or hydrogen/methane, sequential combustion chambers, as present on the Ansaldo Energia H-class GT36, offer a promising solution [5,10]. Due to the dual chamber combustion architecture (Fig. 1), the fuel split ratio between the stages can be varied to account for the different fuel reactivity, thus enabling

fuel flexible firing capabilities [5,9]. The large operational window in combination with the vastly changing combustion properties of alternative carbon-free GT fuels indicate today's relevance for detailed thermoacoustic analysis of novel combustion chambers.

The two axially-staged flames present in sequential combustion chamber architecture use different flame stabilisation mechanisms. The propagation-stabilised flames in the first stage rely on recirculation zones within the flow to anchor the flame [11]. The second stage reheat flame is only partly propagation-stabilised in the shear layer zones. The core of the second flame is predominantly autoignition-stabilised and therefore relies on a constant mean-ignition delay time to position the flame at a desired location in the combustion chamber. While the thermoacoustic response of propagation-stabilised flames have been extensively studied [11–18], auto-ignition flames only recently shifted into the scope of both numerical [19–33] and experimental [34–37] research. Because of their respective flame stabilisation mechanism, the response to perturbations is highly different. Whereas

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Fig. 1. The schematic depicts a dual stage fully premixed sequential combustion architecture.

propagation-stabilised flames are very sensitive to upstream acoustic velocity perturbations, auto-ignition flames react strongly to temperature fluctuations [33,38]. Thereby, temperature changes resulting from both acoustic waves (isentropic) as well as entropy waves (non-isentropic) can strongly influence the flame. Bothien et al. [38] showed that the latter perturbation type originating upstream of the flame tends to be heavily damped due to dissipative effects and decays for higher frequencies. In response to temperature perturbations, the autoignition front moves due to the temperature variations modulating the ignition delay time of the combustion process [21,25].

With respect to the combustion chamber acoustics, transversal combustor eigenmodes remain a topic of high interest [18,39–44]. Berger et al. [45] experimentally investigated the high-frequency response of propagation-stabilised flames and found that the flame brush moves periodically with the pressure amplitude. Later, Berger et al. [34] and McClure et al. [35–37] observed transverse limit-cycle oscillations in an atmospheric reheat combustion chamber. Similarly, it was observed via optical chemiluminescence imaging that the heat release rate response of the flame is in phase with the local pressure oscillations. Furthermore, the heat release rate zone moved towards the high-pressure antinode.

High-fidelity methods exist to numerically analyse thermoacoustic instabilities in detail. Many of them, such as computational fluid dynamics (CFD) employing direct numerical simulation (DNS) or large-eddy-simulation (LES) are very expensive computationally [46], and thus not applicable to be efficiently used for sweeping through geometry iterations and varying operating conditions during combustor development. To fill the gap, computationally efficient low-order techniques are used. Network models have shown to correctly capture planar wave thermoacoustic effects in combustion chambers [42,46–48]. Such models are based on separating the acoustics and the flame dynamics. The acoustic part relies on describing the linearised acoustic behaviour of ducts and area changes using transfer functions and transfer matrices (resulting from conservation equations), which are known from literature [11,13]. The effect of the flame is incorporated in the system by inclusion of experimentally measured or numerically computed flame transfer functions (FTFs) [47]. As a result, these frameworks can perform stability analysis for low-frequency longitudinal eigenmodes. For transverse eigenmodes, the traditional framework assumption of an acoustically compact flame is invalid and conventional models can no longer be used. This is because the length scale of the flame front in the transverse direction is comparable to the wavelength of the acoustic perturbations. Hummel et al. [18,49] developed a low-order network model for transversal mode analysis of propagation-stabilised flames. For the compact flame assumption to regain validity numerically, the flame is segmented into smaller elements and constant perturbations along a segment boundary are assumed. Recently, Rosenkranz et al. [50] extended this work to multi-jet combustors. Low order methods to model and predict thermoacoustically unstable transverse eigenmodes in reheat combustors, as observed in experiments [34,36], remains a gap in research to date.

This study aims to fill the lack of computationally efficient modelling techniques for transverse thermoacoustic modes of reheat combustion chambers. Consequently, a finite element method (FEM) based

code to model the combustor acoustics in tandem with a one-dimensional (1D) Lagrangian model for the flame response is presented to model auto-ignition flames and their thermoacoustic flame response in a two-dimensional (2D) combustor. Thereby, existing reheat flame heat release rate models originally designed for planar wave acoustics are adapted to the transverse case to quantify the local flame response. Because alternatives such as DNS and LES simulations are economically unfeasible for entire combustion chambers at various operating points, the presented work shows great industrial relevance. Furthermore, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first thermoacoustic simulation fully computed in FEM, modelling moving auto-ignition flames in 2D geometries. The novel capability of the framework is demonstrated to predict unstable combustor eigenmodes by validation with experimentally obtained pressure sensor data and chemiluminescence imaging.

2. Experimental reheat combustion chamber and measurement data

The framework is validated against experimental data from a rectangular cross-section atmospheric reheat combustor at the Technical University of Munich (TUM) [35]. The sequential combustor consists of a first and a second combustion stage. For this study, test measurements are used from an operating point firing methane and propane (25% of fuel mass) at an air-fuel ratio of $\lambda_{AFR} = 1.25$ in the reheat combustor. The rectangular combustion chamber with optical access through the quartz side walls allows visualisation of the flame via chemiluminescence imaging for three distinct cross-sections of the combustor (xy -, xz - and yz -plane). The combustor geometry in the xz -plane, shown in Fig. 2, has a constant combustion chamber width of 0.13 m. The small area jump at the dump plane $A_{combustor}/A_{inlet} = 1.3$ was shown to induce negligible shear layer flame propagation in the xz -plane resulting in a predominantly auto-ignition stabilised flame, which is ideal to investigate solely the reheat flame dynamics. The combustor was specifically designed to facilitate the occurrence of transversal modes [51] and ideally suppress low-frequency longitudinal modes. Hence, the inlet is assumed acoustically non-reflecting due to the high damping of the first stage flames. At the outlet, a nozzle guides the exhaust stream into the atmosphere with the intent to induce minimal acoustic reflection, thus, the outlet was assumed acoustically anechoic for our analysis. Measurements from McClure et al. [35] indicate a thermoacoustic instability at 3000 Hz for the TUM combustor. Fig. 3 shows the post-processed measurement signal of the acoustic pressure η , where the probability density function $P(\eta)$, the time signal and the frequency spectrum are shown. The measured 3000 Hz peak in the frequency spectrum was the highest measured acoustic pressure value overall. Further, the bimodal shape of the probability density function indicates a thermoacoustic limit-cycle instability present. In the following sections, all results and geometrical references are made with respect to the results obtained for the xz -cross-section of the TUM combustor, unless specifically stated otherwise. For further details on the reheat combustor and prior experimental findings, the reader is referred to [34,35].

Fig. 2. Schematic of the reheat combustion chamber at TUM in 2D for the xz - and yz -plane.

Fig. 3. Experimental pressure sensor data post-processed to show the probability density function ($P(\eta)$) of the pressure measurement (η), the time signal, and the frequency spectrum.

3. Analytical formulation and numerical methods

Before specifying the technical details on the non-compact thermoacoustic analysis of reheat flames, the mathematical nomenclature that is used from here onwards needs to be defined. Plain symbols such as u without sub- or superscripts stand for the instantaneous value at a point in space. In this case absolute flow velocity. The subscript zero (u_0) stands for the time averaged quantity. The averaging bar (\bar{u}_0) represents the spatially averaged quantity across the duct's diameter or width, which in this case represents the spatially and time averaged flow velocity. Variables with a prime (u') represent the acoustic perturbations, hence acoustic velocity perturbation. The hat (\hat{u}) stands for the perturbation fluctuations in the frequency domain using $u' = \hat{u}e^{i\omega t}$ convention.

3.1. Auto-ignition flame modelling

To quantify a flame response in thermoacoustics, FTFs are used. FTFs relate the heat release rate to an acoustic or hydrodynamic perturbation. Ni et al. [52] were the first to derive a mathematical expression relating the ignition delay time modulation to acoustic pressure pulsations in a sequential combustor. Zellhuber et al. [19] derived an analytical expression for the FTF in the low-frequency regime for 1D auto-ignition fronts. The model describes the flame response to planar acoustic waves with respect to velocity and pressure perturbations (u' , p'). Gant et al. [22] expanded the framework to also capture the effect of temperature and entropic perturbations precisely (T' , s'). The obtained analytical expression was validated with DNS simulations up to 1000 Hz [22] and LES computations of a backwards facing step [23]. Gopalakrishnan et al. [25] developed a numerical 1D-Lagrangian particle framework to model the auto-ignition flame response. Compared to Gant's framework relying on primitive variables, the Lagrangian particle framework relies on scaling the FTFs using the Riemann invariants for up- and downstream travelling acoustic \hat{f} and \hat{g} waves as well as entropic \hat{h} wave (Fig. 4). The transfer functions of both models can be integrated in a FEM based Helmholtz solver. Due to the previous framework validation up to 4000 Hz [25] and its versatile numerical basis, the 1D-Lagrangian numerical framework is coupled to the FEM framework developed here.

Fig. 4. Schematic of a 1D duct with perturbation waves \hat{f}_1 , \hat{g}_1 and \hat{h}_1 upstream of the flame. The flame response \hat{q}_a and flame movement \hat{x}_{ig} computed from the 1D-Lagrangian framework depend on the upstream perturbation waves.

As prior studies showed [22,25] the heat release rate location of reheat flames can vary due to their temperature sensitivity. Eq. (1) states that the mean flame location $x_{ig,0}$ is computed by the product of mean velocity \bar{u}_0 and mean ignition delay time τ_0 .

$$x_{ig,0} = \bar{u}_0 \tau_0 \quad (1)$$

The ignition delay time is sensitive to temperature variations. This can be shown by a set of Cantera zero-dimensional (0D) homogeneous constant pressure reactors which are computed at different initial temperatures. Constant pressure reactors are used, since sequential combustors operate isobaric if the pressure drop due to the flow is neglected. The effect of a temperature increase due to an acoustic wave on the auto-ignition timing can be visualised by an initial temperature sweep of the reactor. A $\pm 3\%$ temperature increase (T'/T_0) with respect to the upstream reference temperature T_0 represents a pressure wave of roughly 10% (p'/p_0) of the mean operating pressure (p_0) according to Eq. (2), where γ is the heat capacity ratio.

$$\frac{T'}{T_0} = \frac{\gamma - 1}{\gamma} \frac{p'}{p_0} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 5 plots the set of Cantera reactors with different starting temperatures. For a temperature increase of 3%, the ignition delay time

Fig. 5. The temperature sensitivity of auto-ignition flames can be shown by a set of 0D homogeneous constant pressure Cantera reactors starting at different initial temperatures ($T_0 \pm T'$).

is reduced by over 40%. Hence, the flame position would shift upstream by 40%. On the contrary, for a lowered inlet temperature of similar magnitude, ignition occurs 80% later and the flame moves downstream. The varying heat release rate location can induce pressure pulsations which can couple with the combustion chamber acoustics and result in thermoacoustic instabilities. Thus, such flame dynamics need to be avoided in GT combustors. For varying equivalence ratios and fuel mixtures, the described sensitivities can change, underlining the importance of modelling thermoacoustic effects in reheat combustion chambers accurately and efficiently during combustion chamber development.

3.2. Eigenfrequency and growth rate calculation with active flames

The frequencies of thermoacoustic instabilities in GT combustors are typically located in close proximity to the natural combustor acoustic eigenfrequencies [46,53], the so called passive flame eigenmodes. Hence, in a combustor this type of instability occurs primarily due to constructive coupling between an acoustic eigenmode and the flame. For zero Mach number flow, the governing equation describing the acoustic field within a volume or area is the Helmholtz equation [54, 55]. The Helmholtz equation is obtained by representing the 2D wave equation in the frequency domain. Assuming no volumetric source term present, the right-hand side of the equation is zero, and the homogeneous Helmholtz equation (Eq. (3)) is obtained

$$\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\rho_0} \nabla \hat{p} \right) + \frac{\omega^2}{\gamma p_0} \hat{p} = 0. \quad (3)$$

Here, ρ_0 is the time averaged density of the fluid, \hat{p} the pressure perturbation in frequency domain and ω the angular frequency. The eigenmodes satisfying this form of the Helmholtz equation and corresponding boundary conditions are the natural acoustic modes of the combustor. By inclusion of a temporally averaged temperature distribution in the combustor due to the flame, the passive flame (non-reacting to acoustic perturbations) eigenmodes can be computed. Prior studies [54,56] showed the effectiveness of FEM modelling to predict thermoacoustic instabilities for quasi 1D configurations (2D simulations in the xy -plane with no variation in y -direction). To compute thermoacoustic eigenmodes and capture the driving effect of active flames, an unsteady source term needs to be added on the right-hand side of the Helmholtz equation. An established $n - \tau$ model [57] was used [54] to correctly capture the heat release rate perturbations of a 1D active flame, where n is an amplitude factor and τ a time delay factor. Nicoud et al. [54] state the unsteady Helmholtz equation Eq. (4) as follows for a $n - \tau$ modelled propagation-stabilised flame [54], where $\hat{q}(x)$ is the heat release rate fluctuation, $n_u(x)$ is the interaction index, δ_f the flame width, \dot{q}_0 the mean volumetric heat release rate, \vec{n}_{ref} the normal vector, $x_{ig,0}$ the average flame position and x_{ref} the reference location where the pressure perturbation is sampled. Solving Eq. (4) numerically in a

finite element (FE) solver using the eigenvalue ansatz $\lambda_{EV} = i(\omega_{re} + i\omega_{im})$ one obtains the eigenfrequencies ($\omega_{re}/2\pi$) and growth rates (ω_{im}).

$$\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\rho_0} \nabla \hat{p} \right) + \frac{\omega^2}{\gamma p_0} \hat{p} = -i\omega \frac{\gamma - 1}{\gamma p_0} \hat{q}(x) \quad (4)$$

with:

$$\hat{q}(x) = \frac{\dot{q}_0}{i\omega \rho_0(x_{ref}) \dot{u}_0} n_u(x) e^{i\omega \tau} \nabla \hat{p}(x_{ref}) \cdot \vec{n}_{ref} \quad (5)$$

$$n_u(x) = \begin{cases} \eta = \frac{\dot{m}_0 \gamma p_0}{\delta_f \dot{q}_0 (\gamma - 1)}, & \text{if } x_{ig,0} - \frac{\delta_f}{2} < x < x_{ig,0} + \frac{\delta_f}{2}, \\ 0 & \text{elsewhere.} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

3.3. Acoustically non-compact auto-ignition flame modelling framework

This section describes the developed framework to capture the coupling effect between transversal eigenmodes and a reheat flame in 2D. The framework consists of a passive flame eigenmode computation, a 1D-Lagrangian particle tracking framework for FTF computation, a Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) CFD simulation to provide information on the mean flame shape and position (or experimental chemiluminescence imaging if available) and a non-compact flame discretisation method. All components are integrated in a FE-model to extract the eigenfrequencies and associated growth rates.

3.3.1. Passive flame eigenmode computation

To compute the passive flame eigenmodes of the combustor, the homogeneous Helmholtz equation (Eq. (3)) is solved using FEM with consideration of a temporally averaged axial temperature distribution in the combustor. Here, the 1D-temperature distribution is defined along the x -axis for the central symmetry line and assumed constant in z -direction. Reheat flames typically operate at inflow velocities in the range of Mach 0.2–0.4, the proposed method, however, assumes zero Mach number by employing the Helmholtz equation. For one, this assumption is believed to be plausible by comparison to studies performing Linearised Euler Equation (LEE) computations [56], where minor changes in the eigenfrequency's real part were found. On top of that, it was found that the eigenmode growth rates tended to further stabilise when capturing flow speed effects. In these scenarios, the flow velocity is aligned with the longitudinal orientation of the quasi 1D duct's eigenmodes. For transversal waves in a simplified scenario, the standing wave of the combustor is perpendicular to the flow direction. Hence, if discretised to transversally orientated Riemann invariants, a direct impact of the mean flow velocity is not evident on the transversal acoustic \hat{f}_z and \hat{g}_z waves. Hence, it is believed that the Helmholtz equation can replicate eigenfrequencies accurately for transversal eigenmodes.

Fig. 6 shows the first transverse (T1z) passive flame eigenmode of the investigated reheat combustor together with the 1D mode shapes for three different cross-sections. The modeshapes are all normalised in the bottom plot. It is observable that all normalised modeshapes of the cross-sections are identical. Thus, it can be assumed that the 2D eigenmodes can be reconstructed by multiplying the normalised eigenmode of the cross-section with a z -coordinate dependent scaling value.

3.3.2. 1D-Lagrangian framework for modeshape dependent FTF computation

The flame response of a 1D compact reheat flame is computed using the 1D-Lagrangian framework [25,27]. The framework is based on capturing the effect of acoustic waves on the ignition process of an auto-ignition flame. The ignition process is numerically simulated using perturbed sets of Cantera 0D reactors, the Lagrangian particles. From the framework a total of six FTFs result. F_1 , F_2 and F_3 which describe the heat release rate response of the autoignition front to downstream-travelling (\hat{f}_1) acoustic wave, upstream-travelling (\hat{g}_1) acoustic wave

Fig. 6. The top image indicates the normalised pressure modeshape of the first transversal eigenmode of the reheat combustion chamber. The middle plot shows the normalised pressure along three cross-sections that are indicated in the first plot. The bottom graph shows the pressure normalised for each cross-section.

and downstream-travelling (\hat{h}_1) entropic wave. Similarly, G_1 , G_2 and G_3 are the corresponding FTFs representing the flame movement. The Riemann invariants are mathematically described in Eq. (7), where c_0 is the speed of sound and \hat{p} the acoustic density perturbation.

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{f} &= \frac{\hat{p} + \rho_0 c_0 \hat{u}}{2} \\ \hat{g} &= \frac{\hat{p} - \rho_0 c_0 \hat{u}}{2} \\ \hat{h} &= c_0^2 \hat{p} - \hat{p}\end{aligned}\quad (7)$$

The superposition of the transfer functions result in Eq. (8) for the normalised integrated heat release rate perturbations $\hat{q}_a/\hat{q}_{0,a}$, and Eq. (9) for the normalised flame movement $\hat{x}_{ig}/x_{ig,0}$, where $\hat{q}_{0,a}$ (W/m^2) is the mean heat release rate per area. The mean heat release rate per area is obtained by integrating the volumetric heat release rate \hat{q}_0 (W/m^3) along the combustor x -axis $\hat{q}_{0,a} = \int_{x_{inlet}}^{x_{outlet}} \hat{q}_0 dx$. The volumetric heat release rate \hat{q}_0 (W/m^3) is computed from 0D constant pressure reactors or calculated using $\hat{q}_0 = \rho_0(x_{ref})\bar{u}_0\Delta h_c = \rho_0(x_{ref})\bar{u}_0c_p(T_{outlet} - T_{inlet})$, where Δh_c is the standard enthalpy of reaction, c_p is the heat capacity at constant pressure and $T_{outlet} - T_{inlet}$ is the temperature difference between the product and reactant flow. The total heat release rate response of the flame can be written as a linear superposition of the individual flame responses to the acoustic and entropy waves:

$$\frac{\hat{q}_a}{\hat{q}_{0,a}} = F_1(\omega)\frac{\hat{f}_1}{\rho_0} + F_2(\omega)\frac{\hat{g}_1}{\rho_0} + F_3(\omega)\frac{\hat{h}_1}{\rho_0}\quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\hat{x}_{ig}}{x_{ig,0}} = G_1(\omega)\frac{\hat{f}_1}{\rho_0} + G_2(\omega)\frac{\hat{g}_1}{\rho_0} + G_3(\omega)\frac{\hat{h}_1}{\rho_0}\quad (9)$$

Model extensions are needed to utilise the 1D-Lagrangian framework [25] to simulate the effect of transversal waves on the ignition process. To derive the framework adaptations in a physics-based modelling approach, multiple assumptions are stipulated. Firstly, purely transversal eigenmodes are a superposition of two transversally travelling waves forming a standing wave, analogous to longitudinal modes with rigid boundary conditions [11]. Thus, with respect to the x -axis, no up- and downstream travelling \hat{f}_x and \hat{g}_x waves are present, but instead the transversal travelling waves \hat{f}_z and \hat{g}_z . While the unsteady flame response to transverse perturbations can induce longitudinal acoustic waves, this effect is hard to model as it is part of the flame-acoustic feedback and cannot be determined *a priori*. Hence, we are neglecting this effect and assume that the influence of the flame induced longitudinal perturbations are minimal. Therefore, a particle that moves downstream the combustor experiences a varying pressure,

temperature and transversal velocity. Transverse velocity fluctuations kinematically change the position of a particle convecting downstream. They result in a harmonic up-and-down motion of the Lagrangian particle in addition to its longitudinal motion. In this work, we neglect the effect of this up-and-down motion of the Lagrangian particle induced by transverse velocity fluctuations on the ignition process and assume that the particle purely moves in the longitudinal direction. To assert this assumption, it was previously shown that velocity fluctuations minimally affect the heat release response of autoignition fronts. The temperature and pressure oscillations, by way of ignition delay modulation, are the main contributor for the flame dynamics [5]. The effect of a purely transversal wave on a Lagrangian particle is thus reduced to its pressure perturbation ($p'(x, t)$), isentropic temperature increase ($T'(x, t)$) and the resulting density variation ($\rho'(x, t)$) which are mathematically described in Eq. (10).

$$\begin{aligned}p'(x, t) &= A_{\psi\Omega}(x)\hat{p}e^{i\omega t + i\phi_A} \\ \rho'(x, t) &= \frac{1}{c_0^2}p'(x, t) \\ T'(x, t) &= \frac{\gamma - 1}{\gamma} \frac{T_0}{p_0}p'(x, t)\end{aligned}\quad (10)$$

In the equations, $\psi_{\Omega}(x)$ represents the modeshape ψ at a certain eigenfrequency Ω , $A_{\psi\Omega}(x)$ the modeshape dependent pressure perturbation amplitude, ϕ_A the phase of the pressure forcing and t the time. With regards to using the framework to model the effect of non-purely transversal eigenmodes which result from a superposition of transversal and longitudinal modes, the longitudinal velocity contributions are neglected in the framework. Further, in case of anechoic boundary conditions some transverse modes can contain outwards travelling acoustic mode shapes. The effect of propagating transverse modes is neglected, and the presented framework assumes standing modeshapes perturbing the ignition process. The effect of pure entropy perturbations, which are hot spots in the exhaust stream of the first combustion stage that are transported to the second stage by the flow, are omitted when computing the overall flame response to purely acoustic eigenmodes. This is for one valid because prior studies showed high-frequency entropic disturbances are strongly dissipated and as such no longer present upon flow entry into the second stage combustion chamber [38]. Also, the aim of this paper is to analyse in detail the coupling effect of transversal eigenmodes and the flame, and not instabilities originating from hot spots generated in the first combustion stage. Thus, the FTFs from Eqs. (8) and (9) are adapted to depend on the perturbation pressure \hat{p} instead of the Riemann invariants to obtain Eqs. (11) and (12).

$$\frac{\hat{q}_{a,\psi\Omega}}{\hat{q}_{0,a}} = F_{\psi\Omega}(\omega)\frac{\hat{p}(x_{ref})}{p_0}\quad (11)$$

$$\frac{\hat{x}_{ig,\psi\Omega}}{x_{ig,0}} = G_{\psi\Omega}(\omega)\frac{\hat{p}(x_{ref})}{p_0}\quad (12)$$

Further, the six FTFs are reduced to solely two FTFs ($F_{\psi\Omega}(\omega) \hat{=} F_1 + F_2 + F_3$ and $G_{\psi\Omega}(\omega) \hat{=} G_1 + G_2 + G_3$), where $F_{\psi\Omega}(\omega)$ stands for the heat release rate, and $G_{\psi\Omega}(\omega)$ for the flame movement. Relating the FTFs with respect to pressure perturbations is in line with the framework of Gant et al. [22]. In case of a partly auto-ignition stabilised flame with heat release also present in the shear layer due to flame propagation, this assumption does no longer hold and an additional flame model would need to be introduced to model the propagation-stabilised flame parts.

The extension to the 1D-Lagrangian framework was developed to capture the effect of a modeshape dependent pressure amplitude perturbation on the ignition process. Hence, if a certain fluid particle within the flow is tracked, it is perturbed by a specific location dependent pressure perturbation, as defined by the pressure modeshape. Fig. 7 shows the evolution of the exerted pressure perturbation on the particle as it is carried downstream and perturbed by the first purely transversal eigenmode. In comparison with a constant amplitude sinusoidal perturbation (cyan curve), the experienced pressure varies greatly. In the

Fig. 7. Pressure the particle experiences during convection under the influence of the first transversal eigenmode (blue) and constant amplitude sinusoidal perturbation (cyan). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

case of the modeshape dependent perturbation the pressure magnitude is limited by the eigenmode's pressure envelope. To obtain the FTF for a specific frequency window, the 1D-Lagrangian framework is computed for multiple frequencies in the range of ± 300 Hz of the passive flame eigenfrequency Ω . To obtain an analytical state space model of the computed FTFs, the Vectorfit [58] system identification tool is used to define the flame response for complex frequency inputs. The obtained analytical expression of the FTFs can subsequently be integrated in the FE-solver.

Fig. 8 plots the FTFs in the investigated frequency range for sinusoidal constant amplitude pressure perturbations starting at different time instances of 0 (cyan) as well as 50% (black) and 80% (magenta) of the mean ignition delay time. Further, the pressure perturbations induced by the first purely transversal modeshape is shown in blue. Differences in the flame response are observed both in the gain and in the phase plots. These differences occur because in the case of the first transversal eigenmode perturbing the particle, the pressure perturbation magnitude only reaches larger values close to the flame region. Hence, the fluctuating pressure acts on the particle late in the ignition process. Such a pressure fluctuation has less of an effect on the ignition delay time modulation, and thus the FTF gain is smaller. On the other hand, the constant amplitude sinusoidal fluctuation starting at $t = 0$ already acts on the particle in the early phase of the ignition process and can thus change the ignition delay time strongly, resulting in higher gains. For comparison, when a constant amplitude sinusoidal pressure perturbation incident from 50% and 80% of the mean ignition delay time is simulated, the resulting FTFs are significantly smaller. This asserts the importance of accounting for modeshape dependent pressure perturbations when using the 1D-Lagrangian framework to model the effect of transversal eigenmodes.

3.3.3. Mean flame shape and location

The 2D framework uses information on the mean flame shape and location which are defined and incorporated using multiple parameters. Parameter $x_{ig,0}(z)$ is the mean flame position on the x -axis and varies along the z -axis. The mean flame shape is determined from either a RANS CFD simulation, or averaged planar chemiluminescence experimental imaging. Prior studies [19,22,27,50] assumed the 1D heat release rate distribution of a reheat flame to be Gaussian shaped Eq. (13). The heat release rate width in the x -direction $\sigma_q(z)$ is computed initially by determining a Gaussian fit of the heat release rate from OD Cantera simulations, analogously to Zellhuber et al. [19].

$$\dot{q}(x, z) = \frac{\dot{q}_{0,a}(z)}{\sigma_q(z)\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x - x_{ig,0}(z)}{\sigma_q(z)}\right)^2\right) \quad (13)$$

Because computations of the width of the heat release rate distribution $\sigma_q(z)$ using Cantera reactors are found to typically underestimate

Fig. 8. The heat release rate FTF obtained from the 1D-Lagrangian framework is plotted for a pressure perturbation by the first transversal eigenmode (blue) and constant amplitude sinusoidal pressure perturbations starting at a time instance of 0 (cyan) as well as 50% (black) and 80% (magenta) of the mean ignition delay time. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 9. The top image shows the normalised contour plot of the experimentally determined mean heat release rate on the xz -plane. The lower plot shows the obtained results by modelling the mean heat release rate using Gaussian curves in x -direction around the peak heat release rate location.

the parameter, the distribution can alternatively be determined from the CFD or experimental data by extracting the Gaussian heat release rate width from the mean fields, as was done here. Fig. 9 shows that the assumption of a Gaussian heat release rate distribution in x -direction and $\sigma_q(z)$ around the peak heat release rate location can approximate the 2D mean heat release rate field. The passive flame temperature distribution can alternatively be simplified using hyperbolic tangent function $\tanh(x)$ [56], or is deduced from CFD simulations or experimental measurements.

3.3.4. Flame segmentation for non-compact flame modelling

To use the derived FTFs for transversally varying pressure perturbations in 1D, the flame needs to be assumed compact in transversal direction. Hummel et al. [18] showed that the flame can numerically be divided into multiple flame segments in transversal direction. Each flame segment is then approximated to have a uniform perturbation input and flame response along its thin height in z -direction, as would be the case for classic plane wave thermoacoustic analysis. The framework presented here does not define confined flame domains, but continuously discretises the flame along the z -axis by stacking multiple thin 1D line segments on top of each other, so called subflames. The

Fig. 10. Depicted is a schematic of the numerical auto-ignition flame segmentation. The flame is segmented by stacking multiple 1D flame segments (N segments) in the z-direction.

procedure of segmenting the averaged flame into multiple 1D subflames is graphically depicted in Fig. 10. The resolution of the flame segmentation is directly linked to the fineness of the numerical FE-mesh, which in this case counted to a minimum of 50 mesh-elements per wavelength $\lambda_{acoustic}$. By employing this type of flame discretisation, very fine segmentation with $\Delta x_{segment}/\lambda_{acoustic} < 0.02$ is achieved. Hence, the assumption is considered numerically valid that a fine 1D segment experiences a uniform pressure perturbation, and therefore responds with a uniform value for heat release rate and flame movement. Each 1D subflame thereby responds to perturbations independently to the adjacent subflames.

The FTFs need to be only computed for one cross-section in x-direction of the combustor's xz-plane, as for all cross-sections of an eigenmode the normalised modeshapes are identical (see Fig. 6). Thus, the same FTF can be applied to each subflame independently to relate the heat release rate response and flame movement linearly to a z-coordinate dependent pressure perturbation at an x-axis reference location x_{ref} directly in front of the flame. A benefit of the presented non-confined flame segmentation is the ability for the flame to move axially during the FE-simulation, since the auto-ignition flame movement can have a big effect on the acoustic analysis, as was shown in previous studies [27,28].

To derive the expression for the heat release rate of a 2D spatially distributed and transversally perturbed auto-ignition flame, the instantaneous heat release rate is multiplied by the FTF $F_{\psi\Omega}(\omega)$ and the Gaussian peak shifted by the FTF $G_{\psi\Omega}(\omega)$. The volumetric heat release rate fluctuation $\hat{q}_{\psi\Omega}(x, z)$ is calculated by subtracting the mean heat release rate at the mean flame location from the instantaneous heat release rate to obtain Eq. (14), where \mathcal{N} stands for the normal distribution.

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{q}_{\psi\Omega}(x, z) &= \frac{\hat{q}_{0,a}(z)}{\sigma_q(z)\sqrt{2\pi}} \left[\exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x - x_{ig,0}(z) - \hat{x}_{ig,\psi\Omega}(z)}{\sigma_q(z)}\right)^2\right) \dots \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left(F_{\psi\Omega}(\omega) \frac{\hat{p}(x_{ref}, z)}{p_0} + 1 \right) - \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x - x_{ig,0}(z)}{\sigma_q(z)}\right)^2\right) \right] \\ &= \hat{q}_{0,a}(z) \left[\mathcal{N}\left(x_{ig,0}(z) + \hat{x}_{ig,\psi\Omega}(z), \sigma_q(z)^2\right) \left(F_{\psi\Omega}(\omega) \hat{p}(x_{ref}, z) p_0^{-1} + 1 \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \mathcal{N}\left(x_{ig,0}(z), \sigma_q(z)^2\right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

with

$$\hat{x}_{ig,\psi\Omega}(z) = x_{ig,0}(z) G_{\psi\Omega}(\omega) \frac{\hat{p}(x_{ref}, z)}{p_0} \quad (15)$$

3.3.5. Inhomogeneous Helmholtz equation for a transversally perturbed moving auto-ignition flame in 2D

The final expression for the inhomogeneous Helmholtz equation for a 2D transversally perturbed and moving auto-ignition flame is obtained by merging the derived methods to obtain the final expression

in Eq. (16). The equation can be numerically solved in a FE-solver in the frequency domain to extract the eigenfrequencies and linear growth rates or perform acoustically forced simulations. In this study COMSOL Multiphysics 6.2 is used [59].

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\rho_0} \nabla \hat{p} \right) + \frac{\omega^2}{\gamma p_0} \hat{p} &= -i\omega \frac{\gamma - 1}{\gamma} \hat{q}_{0,a}(z) \dots \\ \left[\mathcal{N}\left(x_{ig,0}(z) + x_{ig,0}(z) G_{\psi\Omega}(\omega) \hat{p}(x_{ref}, z) p_0^{-1}, \sigma_q(z)^2\right) \left(F_{\psi\Omega}(\omega) \hat{p}(x_{ref}, z) p_0^{-1} + 1 \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \mathcal{N}\left(x_{ig,0}(z), \sigma_q(z)^2\right) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

4. Results

This section shows the results used for framework validation. The framework implementation was initially validated against 1D DNS and Euler equation simulations of hydrogen autoignition-stabilised flames [25,27], where an excellent agreement to the flame response framework adopted in the present paper was observed. To keep the article concise these results are not further discussed. The results of the stability prediction of the reheat combustion chamber are shown and compared to experimentally measured pressure and chemiluminescence data. It needs to be mentioned that given the linearised nature of this framework, the comparison is made between the results of a linear thermoacoustic model and non-linear experimental data. However, we believe the comparison is valid as the goal of the framework is not to reproduce the limit-cycle amplitudes of the heat release rate and pressure fluctuations, but rather to indicate whether a mode is unstable or not. The latter can be further analysed by directly comparing the computed linear growth rate of the numerical model and the time domain analysed linear growth rate from the non-linear experimental data.

4.1. Transversal combustor eigenmode stability analysis

In this section the developed framework is validated against experimental data from the investigated reheat combustion chamber. To perform the growth rate analysis, the passive flame eigenmodes are computed first using the homogeneous Helmholtz equation (Eq. (3)) in FEM considering the mean temperature distribution of the averaged flame. The resulting frequencies and mode shapes give an initial estimate of potential resonance frequencies of the burner and combustor sections [46]. The investigated normalised eigenmodeshapes are depicted in the first column in Fig. 11. Of those frequencies, the first mode corresponds to the first purely transversal (T1z) eigenmode. The other seven investigated modes are a superposition of the first transversal and longitudinal modes. The second column depicts the pressure mode-shape along three different cross sections, indicated on the top left plot. For all modes investigated, the cross-sectional modeshapes are identical after normalising each of them (third column).

Fig. 11. The displayed passive flame eigenmodes (first column) are investigated in terms of their stability. The second column shows the pressure along three distinct cross-sections, which are normalised in the third column.

The effect of the active auto-ignition flame on the purely-acoustic eigenfrequency and its growth rate is captured by solving Eq. (16) for the eigenvalues using FEM. From the eigenvalues result the eigenfrequencies $\text{Re}(\omega)/2\pi$ and growth rates $\text{Im}(\omega)$. The latter is used for the eigenmode stability classification, as positive growth rates indicate an unstable eigenmode. Fig. 12 shows how the first transversal eigenmode at a frequency of 3140 Hz is predicted as unstable. Furthermore, it is the most and only unstable mode throughout the simulation, which is confirmed by the experimental data [35] in Fig. 3 where the 3000 Hz mode showed the strongest pulsations at limit-cycle. The FEM framework is able to capture the frequency of the instability with a deviation of 4%. All other investigated modes show a negative growth rate and are therefore classified as stable, which is confirmed by the experimental data. Further, the sensitivity of the first transversal eigenmode to the outlet boundary conditions was checked. The combustor was specifically designed, that the first transverse eigenmode is unaffected by the boundary conditions. Two additional computations with a pressure release and a choked outlet confirm the eigenmode's insensitivity to the outlet boundary condition, with no change in frequency and a minor change of up to 1.7% in growth rate.

The computed eigenfrequencies and growth rates can further be compared to findings from the experimental pressure sensor data. The measurement duration is 4.5 s for all four mounted sensors. The sensors are mounted on the face plate of the dump plane (Fig. 2). Fig. 13 shows the analysis for two frequencies that are investigated by post-processing the experimental measurement data of the pressure sensors, where η represents pressure measurement. Each eigenfrequency is separately analysed using the methods shown by Noiray et al. [60–62] to extract the pressure probability density function $P(\eta)$, amplitude probability density function $P(A)$, joint probability density function $P(\eta, \dot{\eta}/\omega_0)$ and linear growth rate from the ± 100 Hz around the dominant frequency peak bandpass-filtered time signal envelope. The normalisation of η was done with respect to the 3000 Hz peak for both eigenmodes. Analysing the 3000 Hz frequency, the $P(\eta)$ probability density function shows a distinctive bimodal shape, which indicates a thermoacoustic limit-cycle instability. This is confirmed by observing the $P(\eta, \dot{\eta}/\omega_0)$ joint probability density function, which is also a good indicator of a system's stability. Pulsation data from an unstable mode will show as a circular shaped density in the $\eta, \dot{\eta}$ -plane. In contrary, stable modes will

Fig. 12. The eigenmode stability predictions are shown in the frequency/growth rate plane. The small markers indicate the passive flame eigenfrequencies, and the bigger markers the active flame eigenfrequencies and growth rates.

display a Gaussian-like distribution [61]. The ring-shaped distribution is clearly visible for the 3000 Hz mode, confirming its unstable nature. Time-domain analysis of the pressure sensor data further enables the extraction of the linear growth rate from the non-linear limit cycle oscillation, allowing a quantitative comparison to the framework's computed growth rate. The experimentally measured 3000 Hz mode exhibits a growth rate of 14 rad/s. The developed framework predicts the growth rate to be 26 rad/s. For the latter however, no damping effects were accounted for, which are present in the measurements, explaining the larger value. Romero Vega et al. [51] computed the viscous and thermal damping losses in the boundary layers for the

Fig. 13. The pressure measurement time signal is post-processed for two distinct frequency peaks appearing in the unfiltered frequency spectrum of the time signal. The probability density function of the pressure measurements $P(\eta)$, the time signal, probability density function of the amplitude $P(A)$, the frequency spectrum and the joint probability density function $P(\eta, \dot{\eta}/\omega_0)$ are shown. The measured pressure η is normalised with respect to the 3000 Hz mode.

first transversal mode in y -direction of the investigated reheat combustor. It was found, that the damping rates were very similar between all tested operating points. The first transversal mode in z -direction investigated here produces negligible tangential velocity fluctuations on the combustor wall due to the small step height. Thus, only the thermal damping losses are considered from [51] and scaled by the square root of the frequency in accordance with [63,64] to get a damping rate of 17 rad/s. Subtracting the computed damping rate from the FEM computed growth rate, a final linear growth rate result of 9 rad/s is obtained for the unstable 3140 Hz mode including damping effects in the acoustic boundary layer. This value is very close to the linear growth rate estimate from the experimental pressure sensor data of 14 rad/s and is considered an accurate result. This result is further supported by other studies on comparably sized geometries that computed growth rates of a similar value [65,66].

To visualise the time-domain analysis result of a stable mode, the lower graph in Fig. 13 shows the results for the 3500 Hz frequency peak. The stable nature of this eigenmode can be seen by the unimodal pressure probability density function and the Gaussian-like $P(\eta, \dot{\eta}/\omega_0)$ graph. The eigenfrequency of a stable mode can still be experimentally measured if the resonance is driven by another unstable mode, in this case the 3000 Hz mode. Hence, the measured peaks in the frequency domain correspond to measured resonance frequencies and not thermoacoustic instabilities. All remaining measured peaks in Fig. 3 were analysed and found to be stable.

How the auto-ignition flame behaves locally can be investigated via chemiluminescence imaging through the quartz sidewall of the combustor. The images were captured at a sampling rate of 13500 s^{-1} at a resolution of 1.6 px/mm [35]. The flame response of the experimentally measured limit-cycle oscillation at 3000 Hz can be qualitatively compared to a transversally forced FEM simulation by investigation of the normalised heat release rate fluctuations at different phases of the pressure oscillation. For the forced simulation the identical 3000 Hz frequency as experimentally measured is chosen and not the predicted eigenfrequency of 3140 Hz. Fig. 14 shows the pressure field in the combustor at 30° phase steps during half an oscillation cycle in the first column, the numerical heat release rate fluctuations in the second column, and the experimental heat release rate fluctuations in the third column. The dashed grey contour line represents the mean flame

shape. For a positive pressure anti-node in the 0° phase plot, the auto-ignition flame front moves upstream, due to the earlier timed ignition of the fuel/air mixture. Also, the heat release rate magnitude is greater towards the outside of the combustor, near the combustor wall. This is because the heat release rate perturbation magnitude scales linearly with the pressure perturbation and the pressure anti-nodes are located near the combustor walls. Towards the pressure node at the centre of the combustor, the flame response retains the identical phase but weakens in magnitude due to the lower p' value. Directly on the nodal line, the heat release rate fluctuation is zero. Towards the opposite negative pressure anti-node, the lack of heat release rate gradually intensifies and the flame moves downstream. For the plotted phase sequence from $0-180^\circ$, it is observed that the numerical and experimental heat release rate are in phase with the pressure perturbation. A qualitatively good agreement between numerically computed and experimentally measured normalised heat release rate fluctuations is thus shown.

Further analysis in Fig. 15 shows quantitatively the integrated heat release rate during one harmonic cycle for both the numerical computation and the experimental chemiluminescence imaging. The integration is done for three different cross-sections, which are depicted in the bottom left plot in Fig. 14 and correspond to the z -coordinates 0.01 m (cyan), 0.02 m (blue) and 0.03 m (magenta). The values are normalised by the maximum integrated heat release rate obtained in the outer most segment numerically as well as experimentally. It is visible, that for all three different cross-sections, the numerical result qualitatively matches the experimental data. Additionally, the heat release rate curves for the different cross-sections are in-phase, which supports the initially made assumption of discretising the flame by multiple stacked 1D subflames in the z -direction and scaling the heat release rate according to the local pressure value.

5. Conclusions

Transversal combustion instabilities remain of high importance in modern gas turbine combustor development. Therefore, the prediction of unstable transverse modes in reheat combustors is of growing academic and industrial interest, with the respective modelling methods thereof still in their early development stages. This paper contributes

Fig. 14. The 2D normalised heat release rate perturbation is qualitatively analysed between the FE-result (second column) and the experimental chemiluminescence imaging (third column). The comparison is done for different phases of the pressure oscillation (first column) in 30° steps for half an oscillation period. The mean flame shape is indicated by the dashed grey contour line.

Fig. 15. The integrated heat release rate along three cross-sections is qualitatively compared between the experimentally obtained chemiluminescence imaging and the FE-computation. The comparison is done for cross-sections at different z -coordinates, indicated on the bottom left plot in Fig. 14. The values are normalised by the numerical and experimental heat release rate values of the outermost segments.

to filling the gap of available thermoacoustically non-compact reheat flame modelling techniques by showing the complete development of a 2D-FEM based Lagrangian method coupled framework to capture the effect transversally perturbed auto-ignition flames have on the combustor's thermoacoustic stability. To achieve this, the framework was firstly validated by comparison to DNS and Euler computations performed with and without planar wave forcing. Consequently, the developed framework was used to perform stability and eigenfrequency predictions for an atmospheric reheat combustor burning fully premixed methane and propane at a lean equivalence ratio. Results are in good agreement with experimentally obtained pressure sensor measurements and chemiluminescence imaging. The use case of this framework is twofold. For one, in a continued academic study further framework improvements can be made in order to also capture other effects and improve accuracy. To do so, a next step could be to adapt the framework to perform thermoacoustic analysis in 3D volumes. Further, reheat flames as they are present in industrial combustors are never fully auto-ignition stabilised. Typically, certain sections of the flame

will be propagation-stabilised, usually in the hydrodynamic shear-layers. Consequently, these flame regions behave differently and could potentially be modelled using a $n-\tau$ flame model to realistically capture their heat release rate and superimpose them with the auto-ignition front's numerical model. Lastly, the presented model assumes a perfectly premixed air and fuel state at the combustor inlet. In real systems however, only the technically premixed state is present, which leads to fuel-rich spots being transported downstream resulting in hot spots of higher heat release rate. Such effects could potentially be captured by solving the LEE or Linearised Navier Stokes Equations (LNSE), which however comes with increased computational complexity [46]. The other targeted use case is in industrial combustion chamber development. Due to the low computational cost associated with the presented framework's computation, stability predictions can efficiently be made during rapid prototyping phases. Sweeping through various geometries to converge to specific combustor shapes or flame placements that mitigate thermoacoustic instabilities in an early design phase is possible and of high relevance for modern GT development.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Simon M. Heinzmann: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Harish S. Gopalakrishnan:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Francesco Gant:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Mirko R. Bothien:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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References

- [1] United Nations, Paris agreement, 2015.
- [2] International Energy Agency, World energy outlook 2022, 2022.
- [3] Bundesamt für Energie, Energieperspektiven 2050+, 2021.
- [4] Expert Group Security of Supply ETH Zurich, Energy security in a net zero emissions future for Switzerland, 2023.
- [5] M.R. Bothien, A. Ciani, J.P. Wood, G. Fruechtel, Toward decarbonized power generation with gas turbines by using sequential combustion for burning hydrogen, *J. Eng. Gas Turbines Power* 141 (2019).
- [6] H. Farhat, C. Salvini, Novel gas turbine challenges to support the clean energy transition, *Energies* 15 (2022).
- [7] J. Goldmeier, C. Buck, B. Suleiman, H. Selim, K. Tayebi, G.-L. Agostinelli, A. Dawood, Techno-economic analysis of hydrogen and ammonia as low carbon fuels for power generation, in: *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2023*, 2023.
- [8] M. Kloess, K. Zach, Bulk electricity storage technologies for load-leveling operation - An economic assessment for the Austrian and German power market, *Int. J. Electr. Power Energy Syst.* 59 (2014) 111–122.

- [9] A. Ciani, M. Bothien, B. Bunkute, J. Wood, G. Fruechtel, Superior fuel and operational flexibility of sequential combustion in ansaldo energia gas turbines, *J. Glob. Power Propuls. Soc.* 3 (2019) 630–638.
- [10] T. Heggset, O. Meyer, A. Gruber, L. Tay-Wo-Chong, A. Ciani, Numerical assessment of a rich-quench-lean staging strategy for clean and efficient combustion of partially decomposed ammonia in the constant pressure sequential combustion system, in: *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2023 Turbomachinery Technical Conference and Exposition*, GT2023, 2023.
- [11] T.C. Lieuwen, *Unsteady Combustor Physics*, Cambridge University Press, 2012.
- [12] C.J. Lawn, W. Polifke, A model for the thermoacoustic response of a premixed swirl burner, Part II: The flame response, *Combust. Sci. Technol.* 176 (2004) 1359–1390.
- [13] T. Poinso, D. Veynante, *Theoretical and Numerical Combustion*, Second ed., Edwards Inc., 2005.
- [14] B. Schuermans, V. Bellucci, F. Guethé, F. Meili, P. Flohr, C.O. Paschereit, A detailed analysis of thermoacoustic interaction mechanisms in a turbulent premixed flame, in: *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2004 Power for Land, Sea, and Air*, 2004.
- [15] T. Lieuwen, Modeling premixed combustion-acoustic wave interactions: A review, *J. Propuls. Power* 19 (2003) 765–781.
- [16] A. Huber, W. Polifke, Dynamics of practical premixed flames, part I: model structure and identification, *Int. J. Spray Combust. Dyn.* (2009) 199.
- [17] A. Huber, W. Polifke, Dynamics of practical premixed flames, part II: identification and interpretation of CFD data, *Int. J. Spray Combust. Dyn.* (2009) 229.
- [18] T. Hummel, C. Temmler, B. Schuermans, T. Sattelmayer, Reduced order modeling of aeroacoustic systems for stability analyses of thermoacoustically non-compact gas turbine combustors, in: *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2015: Turbine Technical Conference and Exposition*, 2015.
- [19] M. Zellhuber, V. Bellucci, B. Schuermans, W. Polifke, Modelling the impact of acoustic pressure waves on auto-ignition flame dynamics, in: *Proceedings of the European Combustion Meeting 2011*, 2011.
- [20] M. Zellhuber, B. Schuermans, W. Polifke, Impact of acoustic pressure on autoignition and heat release, *Combust. Theory Model.* 18 (2014) 1–31.
- [21] F. Gant, A. Scarpato, M.R. Bothien, Occurrence of multiple flame fronts in reheat combustors, *Combust. Flame* 205 (2019) 220–230.
- [22] F. Gant, A. Gruber, M.R. Bothien, Development and validation study of a 1D analytical model for the response of reheat flames to entropy waves, *Combust. Flame* 222 (2020) 305–316.
- [23] F. Gant, A. Cuquel, M.R. Bothien, Autoignition flame transfer matrix: Analytical model versus large eddy simulations, *Int. J. Spray Combust. Dyn.* 14 (2022) 72–81.
- [24] A. Gruber, M.R. Bothien, A. Ciani, K. Aditya, J.H. Chen, F.A. Williams, Direct numerical simulation of hydrogen combustion at auto-ignitive conditions: Ignition, stability and turbulent reaction-front velocity, *Combust. Flame* 229 (2021).
- [25] H.S. Gopalakrishnan, A. Gruber, J. Moeck, Response of auto-ignition-stabilized flames to one-dimensional disturbances: Intrinsic response, *J. Eng. Gas Turbines Power* 143 (2021).
- [26] H.S. Gopalakrishnan, T. Heggset, A. Gruber, J. Moeck, Prediction of autoignition-stabilized flame dynamics in a backward-facing step reheat combustor, in: *Proceedings of Combustion Institute-Canadian Section Spring Technical Meeting the University of Ottawa*, 2022.
- [27] H.S. Gopalakrishnan, A. Gruber, J.P. Moeck, Computation and prediction of intrinsic thermoacoustic oscillations associated with autoignition fronts, *Combust. Flame* 254 (2023).
- [28] H.S. Gopalakrishnan, T. Heggset, A. Gruber, M.R. Bothien, J. Moeck, Prediction of autoignition-stabilized flame dynamics in a backward-facing step reheat combustor configuration, in: *Symposium on Thermoacoustics in Combustion: Industry Meets Academia*, SoTiC 2023, 2023.
- [29] H.S. Gopalakrishnan, A. Gruber, J. Moeck, Computation of intrinsic instability and sound generation from auto-ignition fronts, *J. Eng. Gas Turbines Power* 145 (2023).
- [30] O. Schulz, T. Jaravel, T. Poinso, B. Cuenot, N. Noiray, A criterion to distinguish autoignition and propagation applied to a lifted methane-air jet flame, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 36 (2017) 1637–1644.
- [31] O. Schulz, N. Noiray, Autoignition flame dynamics in sequential combustors, *Combust. Flame* 192 (2018) 86–100.
- [32] K. Aditya, A. Gruber, C. Xu, T. Lu, A. Krisman, M.R. Bothien, J.H. Chen, Direct numerical simulation of flame stabilization assisted by autoignition in a reheat gas turbine combustor, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 37 (2019) 2635–2642.
- [33] A. Scarpato, L. Zander, R. Kulkarni, B. Schuermans, Identification of multi-parameter flame transfer function for a reheat combustor, in: *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2016*, 2016.
- [34] F.M. Berger, T. Hummel, P.R. Vega, B. Schuermans, T. Sattelmayer, A novel reheat combustor experiment for the analysis of high-frequency flame dynamics - concept and experimental validation, in: *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2018 Turbomachinery Technical Conference and Exposition*, 2018.
- [35] J. McClure, F.M. Berger, M. Bertsch, B. Schuermans, T. Sattelmayer, Self-excited high-frequency transverse limit-cycle oscillations and associated flame dynamics in a gas turbine reheat combustor experiment, in: *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2021 Turbomachinery Technical Conference and Exposition*, 2021.

- [36] J. McClure, F.M. Berger, M. Bertsch, B. Schuermans, T. Sattelmayer, Observation of reactive shear layer modulation associated with high-frequency transverse thermoacoustic oscillations in a gas turbine reheat combustor experiment, *Int. J. Spray Combust. Dyn.* 14 (2022) 131–142.
- [37] J. McClure, M. Bothien, T. Sattelmayer, Autoignition delay modulation by high-frequency thermoacoustic oscillations in reheat flames, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 39 (2023) 4691–4700.
- [38] M. Bothien, D. Lauper, Y. Yang, A. Scarpatò, Reconstruction and analysis of the acoustic transfer matrix of a reheat flame from large-eddy simulations, *J. Eng. Gas Turbines Power* 141 (2019).
- [39] N. Noiray, M. Bothien, B. Schuermans, Analytical and Numerical Analysis of Staging Concepts in Annular Gas Turbines, Summer School and Workshop on Non-Normal and Nonlinear Effects in Aero- and Thermoacoustics, Munich, 2010.
- [40] T. Poinsot, Prediction and control of combustion instabilities in real engines, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 36 (2017) 1–28.
- [41] D. Laera, T. Schuller, K. Prieur, D. Durox, S.M. Camporeale, S. Candel, Flame describing function analysis of spinning and standing modes in an annular combustor and comparison with experiments, *Combust. Flame* 184 (2017) 136–152.
- [42] M.R. Bothien, N. Noiray, B. Schuermans, Analysis of azimuthal thermo-acoustic modes in annular gas turbine combustion chambers, *J. Eng. Gas Turbines Power* 137 (2015).
- [43] N.A. Worth, J.R. Dawson, Modal dynamics of self-excited azimuthal instabilities in an annular combustion chamber, *Combust. Flame* 160 (2013) 2476–2489.
- [44] G. Ghirardo, M.P. Juniper, M.R. Bothien, The effect of the flame phase on thermoacoustic instabilities, *Combust. Flame* 187 (2017) 165–184.
- [45] F.M. Berger, T. Hummel, M. Hertweck, J. Kaufmann, B. Schuermans, T. Sattelmayer, High frequency thermoacoustic modulation mechanisms in swirl-stabilized gas turbine combustors: Part one experimental investigation of local flame response, in: *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2016: Turbomachinery Technical Conference and Exposition*, 2016.
- [46] W. Polifke, Six lectures on thermoacoustic combustion instability, 2015.
- [47] M.R. Bothien, J.P. Moeck, A. Lacarelle, C.O. Paschereit, Time domain modelling and stability analysis of complex thermoacoustic systems, *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part A: J. Power Energy* 221 (2007) 657–668.
- [48] B. Schuermans, F. Guethe, D. Pennell, D. Guyot, C.O. Paschereit, Thermoacoustic modeling of a gas turbine using transfer functions measured under full engine pressure, *J. Eng. Gas Turbines Power* 132 (2010).
- [49] T. Hummel, F. Berger, M. Hertweck, B. Schuermans, T. Sattelmayer, High-frequency thermoacoustic modulation mechanisms in swirl-stabilized gas turbine combustors part two: Modeling and analysis, in: *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2016: Turbomachinery Technical Conference and Exposition*, 2016.
- [50] J.-A. Rosenkranz, J. Neu, T. Sattelmayer, Network-and CFD/CAA-Modelling of the high frequency flame response in multi-jet combustors, in: *Symposium on Thermoacoustics in Combustion: Industry Meets Academia (SoTiC 2023)*, vol. 14, 2023, p. 2023.
- [51] P.R. Vega, F.M. Berger, T. Hummel, B. Schuermans, T. Sattelmayer, Numerical design of a novel reheat combustor experiment for the analysis of high-frequency flame dynamics, in: *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2018*, 2018.
- [52] A. Ni, W. Polifke, F. Joos, Ignition delay time modulation as a contribution to thermo-acoustic instability in sequential combustion, in: *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2000*, 2000.
- [53] C.F. Silva, Intrinsic thermoacoustic instabilities, *Prog. Energy Combust. Sci.* 95 (2023).
- [54] F. Nicoud, L. Benoit, C. Sensiau, T. Poinsot, P. Thierry, Acoustic modes in combustors with complex impedances and multidimensional active flames, *AIAA J.* 45 (2007) 426–441.
- [55] C. Laurent, M. Bauerheim, T. Poinsot, F. Nicoud, A novel modal expansion method for low-order modeling of thermoacoustic instabilities in complex geometries, *Combust. Flame* 206 (2019) 206.
- [56] K. Wiczeorek, F. Nicoud, Prediction of thermoacoustic instabilities: Numerical study of mach number effects, 2006.
- [57] L. Crocco, Aspects of combustion stability in liquid propellant rocket motors Part I: Fundamentals. Low frequency instability with monopropellants, *J. Am. Rocket Soc.* 21 (1951) 163–178.
- [58] B. Gustavsen, A. Semlyen, Rational approximation of frequency domain responses by vector fitting, *IEEE Trans. Power Deliv.* 14 (1999).
- [59] COMSOL, COMSOL multiphysics reference manual, 2023.
- [60] N. Noiray, B. Schuermans, Deterministic quantities characterizing noise driven hopf bifurcations in gas turbine combustors, *Int. J. Non-Linear Mech.* 50 (2013) 152–163.
- [61] N. Noiray, Linear growth rate estimation from dynamics and statistics of acoustic signal envelope in turbulent combustors, *J. Eng. Gas Turbines Power* 139 (2017).
- [62] N. Noiray, A. Denisov, A method to identify thermoacoustic growth rates in combustion chambers from dynamic pressure time series, *Proc. Combust. Inst.* 36 (2017) 3843–3850.
- [63] P. Romero, T. Hummel, F.M. Berger, B. Schuermans, T. Sattelmayer, Damping due to the acoustic boundary layer for high-frequency transverse modes, in: *24th International Congress on Sound and Vibration*, London, 2017.
- [64] F.E.C. Culick, *Unsteady Motions in Combustion Chambers for Propulsion Systems*, North Atlantic Treaty Organization, Research and Technology Organization, RTO of NATO, 2006.
- [65] T. Hofmeister, T. Sattelmayer, Reduced order modeling of modal suppression processes between two transversal modes in a swirl-stabilized lean-premixed gas turbine combustor, 2021.
- [66] T. Hummel, K. Hammer, P. Romero, B. Schuermans, T. Sattelmayer, Low-order modeling of nonlinear high-frequency transversal thermoacoustic oscillations in gas turbine combustors, in: *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo 2016: Turbomachinery Technical Conference and Exposition*, GT2016, 2016.